

The Effect of Using Online Discussion on 9th Grade Female Students Speaking Skills in Jordan and their Attitude Toward it

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 21, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 22, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Using Online Discussion, Speaking Skills. 9th Grade Female Students.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5799689</p>	<p><i>The purpose of this research was to find out more about the Effect of Using Online Discussion on 9th Grade Female Students Speaking Skills in Jordan and their Attitude Toward it. The aim of the study was to find answers to the following questions:</i></p> <p><i>Q1: Are there significant differences between mean scores of the experimental and control groups 9th Grade Female students' performance in the students' learning Speaking Skills due to the method of using (Using Online Discussion VS the conventional method)?</i></p> <p><i>Q2: Are there any significant differences between the experimental group and control group 9th Grade Female students' mastery of Speaking Skills learning due to using Online Discussion to explained speaking Skills?</i></p> <p><i>Q3: What are the experimental group Female students' attitudes toward using Online Discussion and its effect on their Attitude Toward it? The participant of the study consisted of (60) 9th Grade Female Students at AlkomAlahmer Secondary School During the first semester of the 2020/2021 academic year. The study's sample consisted of two groups: The first group comprised of thirty (30) female students and group two consisted of (30) Female students. There were two parts to the pre-test and post-test; a Speaking Skills tests that tested Female students' ability to interact appropriately in communicative settings and a questionnaire.</i></p>

Introduction

English is becoming increasingly important around the world in general, and particularly in Jordan. While some in Jordan Students, haven't regular contact with English-speaking, only a few Jordanians lived close to English-speaking groups. Furthermore, there are no English native or near native speaking teachers in Jordanian government schools. All of these factors make it more difficult for most Jordanians to speak English as a significant oral producing talent.

Students considered the input of the educational process at every educational institution, and so enhancing their academic performance is one of the most important outcomes of the educational process. However, a number of circumstances frequently influence this performance, causing pupils' academic levels to deteriorate. As long as female English 9th grade students are included in this group, they cannot be removed from the overall academic and speaking skills weakness that has begun to emerge in Jordanian schools. (Elkhafaifi, 2005).

Students achievement are the ultimate goal of the educational process. Achievement Known as the measurement of the amount of academic content a student learns It is well known that using online discussion has a positive impact on student achievement. Previous studies have shown that using Online Discussion can help students achieve better results. (Jacob, 2012).

Background of the study

Nowadays, Politics, economics, technology, and education are all conducted in English. In this respect, School pupils, as well as many regular people, are interested in studying English because they believe it will open up many job chances. Moreover, they think that learning English can make them interact with many new cultures more easily and effectively.

The purpose of English teaching and learning is to focus on female students so that They can communicate in English as well as use it to improve their education. The Speaking Skills are used simultaneously during the teaching and learning process. Learners in an English Speaking Skills class rarely apply the language in a real-life setting They are unable to effectively and responsibly communicate. As a result, learners lose confidence in themselves and avoid interacting in English.

Speaking Skills

Unless the speaker is talking to what the student is watching or the language being studied is directly related to another language the student is familiar with, the student will struggle to grasp anything. During Understanding activities, the student can comprehend particular vocabulary and grammatical structures, which will help the

student understand more in stage two, when she or he is able to speak in a simple manner. After completing stage one, the learner has a sufficient understanding of the language's core building blocks to begin haltingly functioning in real-life communication circumstances. There isn't much substantial speaking skill in stage one, except from a few words and sentences that can be built on the Understanding activities. The student must rely on taught survival phrases to meet the most immediate demand in real-life communication situations. (Bashir, & Azeem, & Dogar, 2011).

Statement of the problem

The studies on language teaching and learning had been shown that one of the common problems that face learners is the lack of interest in Speaking Skills. Moreover, teachers are teaching in the classroom and there is no use of contemporary methods of teaching. The learners may be afraid of making errors or being criticized by others especially their teachers. Moreover, the classroom environment is not well prepared for a Using Online Discussion and the traditional methods of teaching Speaking Skills, are still dominant in the many class and not Using Online Discussion on 9th Grade Female Students.

furthermore, students are studying English for twelve years, but they cannot Speaking English. This might be due to the fact that they may not have real opportunities to practice Speaking Skills y. in addition, the researcher believes that teaching Speaking Skills through conventional ways may not encourage and help students to practice the target Speaking Skills naturally, and not using Modern methods in learning like Online Discussion.

Purpose of the study

The goal of this study is to see how using online discussion improves the speaking skills of 9th grade female students in Jordan, as well as their attitude about it. And, if it is better than the traditional method of teaching or not. It also aims to know the advantages and disadvantages of the system Using Online Discussion and how can we improve it?

Significance of the Study

The finding of the study might be officially adopted by the Ministry of Education to encourage teachers to Using Online Discussion. By using online discussion into an interaction English community, Speaking Skills can help pupils overcome their fears and shyness. In addition, Teachers can employ interactive dialogues on a variety of themes to help them break free from their normal teaching routines, transforming the classroom into a Using Online Discussion. This research could be useful to curriculum designers, in the sense that they may build their English language textbook on the trends of Using Online Discussion in classes.

Questions of the study

The study attempts to answer the following three questions:

1. Are there significant differences between mean scores of the experimental and control groups 9th Grade Female students' performance in the students' learning Speaking Skills due to the method of using (Using Online Discussion VS the conventional method)?.
2. Are there any significant differences between the experimental group and control group 9th Grade Female students' mastery of Speaking Skills learning due to using Online Discussion to explained speaking Skills?.
3. What are the experimental group Female students' attitudes toward using Online Discussion and its effect on their Attitude Toward it?

Hypotheses of the study

1. Between the experimental and control groups, there are no statistically significant differences. Due to the way of using, female students' mean scores in the students' gaining speaking skills (Using Online Discussion vs. conventional method).
2. Due to the use of Online Discussion of teaching students' speaking Skills, there are no statistically significant differences in the experimental group Female students' mastery of each of the students' teaching speaking Skills.
3. The experimental group Female students' have positive attitudes toward Using Online Discussion and it's on their Attitude Toward it.

definitions of terms

Effect: the impact of using online discussion On 9th Grade female student and their attitude toward it.

Online Discussion: It refers to using English as if students live in an English village. They use English all the time to get their needs and to express their feeling. This can be achieved on variety functions and topics in variety environment.

Speaking Skills: It refers to the use of natural language by native speakers to provide continuous discourse and meaning for the listener without difficulty. It entails both listening and speaking abilities. It also refers to comprehending English at various speeds, in various contexts, and in the presence of noise.

Limitations of the study

-The sample size is small, as it only comprises a small group of 9th grade students from the Directorate of Education Northeast Badia in Mafrak Region during the first semester of the 2020/21 academic year.

-The duration of the research is limited to a period of 7 weeks. It is also limited to Using Online Discussion and its effect on 9th grade students' Speaking Skills.

Theoretical background

Discussion boards are a terrific way to get students involved in an online classroom. They're nearly everywhere; they're a part of every virtual classroom and every school curriculum. In an ideal world, the boards would promote not only student engagement but also critical thinking and a feeling of community in online spaces.

An online discussion occurs when a teacher uses software to encourage online discussions among students or teachers on a specific topic. While online technologies have many parallels to approaches for developing face-to-face interactions, they have distinct advantages and disadvantages when it comes to creating meaningful connections between students and instructors. (An, et al, 2009).

Online discussion tool:

Google Groups and Office 365 Groups are not linked to any specific course because they are not integrated with an LMS. However, you can access them through your Canvas course. One of them may be a better fit for what you want to achieve through online chats, depending on your needs. (Google Office 365, 2020).

Teaching Speaking

Many language learners consider speaking ability to be a criterion for mastery of a language. Fluency, according to these students, is defined as the capacity to converse with people rather than the ability to read, write, or understand oral language. They consider that speaking is the most important talent they can learn, and that their capacity to communicate effectively is how they assess their success.

Language learners must understand that speaking requires three types of knowledge:

- Mechanics (pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary): Using the correct words in the correct order and with proper pronunciation.
- Functions (transaction and interaction): Recognizing when message clarity is critical (transaction/information exchange) and when it is not (interaction/relationship development).
- Social and cultural rules and norms (turn-taking, speaking rate, length of pauses between speakers, participants' relative roles): Knowing how to take into consideration who is speaking to whom. What circumstances, what is it about, and why are you doing it? (John, 2002).

Literature Review

The Effect of Using Online Discussion on 9th Grade Students' Speaking Skills in Jordan and Their Attitude Toward It will be covered in this chapter.

Kyunghinet al. (2019) investigated the impact of various forms of teacher remarks on student connection in an online debate in a recent study. This study looked at three types of comments: (1) laudation-oriented comments, which accept students' initial messages and brief them on their topic, (2) description-enhancing comments, which demand a description of the first messages, and (3) view-extending comments, which offer various or thought-provoking views replaying the first messages. An online course enrolled a total of seventeen graduate students. The degrees of knowledge structure were assessed using a content analysis. The number of posts and subject units were used to measure communication. The researchers discovered that view-widening comments made it easier for students to test their knowledge on peer postings by bringing up a variety of perspectives. However, although elaboration-motivating comments result in the highest levels of response between students, the level of response was unaffected by laudatory comments.

Zhong et al. (2017) studied Improving the English-speaking skills of young learners through mobile social networking, the majority of English as a foreign language (EFL) students do not have adequate opportunity to practice speaking English. While the current evolution of social networking sites (SNSs) and mobile teaching, particularly mobile-assisted language training, provides these students with additional chances to successfully practice speaking English. The purpose of this study was to see how a mobile SNS affected the learners' speaking skills in first-grade EFL classrooms in China. Students were divided into two groups, one as a control group who did not use the SNS and the other as an experimental group who did. While both classes improved their speaking skills between the pretest and posttest, the experimental group's gains in English fluency were significantly greater. On the other hand, there were similarities in accuracy and pronunciation between the two groups. These findings are discussed in light of the features of social networking sites and mobile learning that allow learners to communicate in low-stress, situational scenarios.

Alzahrani (2017) studied the impact of using online discussion forums (ODFs) on learner' learning, specifically on their achievement. To achieve this, a quasi-experimental design was implemented at one of Saudi Arabia's major institutions for one academic semester. Undergraduate students (N = 138) were divided into two groups for this study: the experimental group included 67 students and the control group included 71 students. The findings suggest that employing ODFs has a similar effect on students' achievement. Furthermore, statistical analysis reveals a strong and positive relationship between learner sharing in ODFs and their last course grade, but no such relationship exists between learner sharing in ODFs and grade point rate. The increased performance

when students use ODFs to promote informal learning is likely due to the communication interaction and cooperative character of ODFs environments, as well as effective teaching in mixed teaching courses. On the other hand, contextual distance needs to be given a great awareness to get gratification outcomes.

AlJeraisy et al. (2015) looked into the effect of employing online discussion forums on student achievement in a private university's Faculty of Business Administration course. The participants in the study were divided into two groups of 60 pupils, each of which used Moodle. Only the experimental group had access to online discussion forums (ODFs). They indicated that those who had access to ODFs performed much better on the unit exam than those who did not. In addition, Students who had access to ODFs exhibited more confidence in their exam results because a large number of them assessed their intuition as outstanding or very good.

Ravi (2014) studied the Effectiveness of Using Online Discussion Forum for Case Study Analysis, Business schools are experimenting with novel pedagogical approaches to learning in order to address issues such as increased class sizes, limited budget, and barriers to facilitating and increasing effective participation and learning across various groups of students. This study is based on the results of a validation study of a pedagogical method that incorporates an online discussion board and a case study. By analyzing the quantity and quality of online sending and comparing accounting students' performance to that of a prior group, this study indicates a significant level of perfection in learner learning. An appropriate design and delivery tactics, as well as clear assessment criteria for assessment and use, have aided students in overcoming their own language hurdles and enhancing their ability to participate in a non-threatening environment. This strategy boosted the benefits of peer-to-peer learning and case study education. However, reported increases in student workload and marking load for academics, there are some of the challenges that academics should investigate more, as well as determining the value of learning.

Lynn et al. (2009) studied Reversal Using an Online Discussion Forum: Effect on learner Learning and gratification, the quasi-experimental study investigated whether learners were more relieved and learnt more via an online discussion with parallels or a hardcopy reversal with one-time teacher comments. A t test was used to determine the difference between an experimental and a comparison part of the same course: post-course evaluations on how well the course objectives were accomplished, what students intended to learn from the course, course satisfaction, and end-of-semester grades for learners. Students who participated in weekly online discussions with peers had a higher rate of attaining the goals they set for themselves in the course than those who submitted weekly hardcopy reversals with a one-time facilitator/instructor influence. In their course part, the learner demonstrated a preference for the method of influence used. On the other hand, the students' ages were found to be a significant impact in their preference for online interaction. There were substantial variations between the groups when it came to assessing how effectively the course content had been learned, but not when it came to course satisfaction or grades.

Concluding Remark

All the previous studies dealt with using online discussion and its impact on language learning. Several previous studies indicated that there is a strong relationship between using online discussion in a small English community and its positive effect on the EFL student's performance. However, what distinguishes this study from other studies is that it tackled the effect of using online discussion on EFL students' performance and attitude at the same time.

Methods and procedures:

Design of the Study

During the first semester of the school year 2020/2021, the study's experiment will be conducted for 6 weeks. The study's sample will include (60) female students. The experimental group's subjects will be exposed to the Using Online Discussion for 6 weeks. The subjects in the control group, on the other hand, will receive regular education in teaching Speaking Skills using printed materials for the same time period. A pre-test will be given to all groups before the treatment to ensure that they are equivalent, and the same test will be given as a post-test after the treatment to see if the Using Online Discussion has any effect on the experimental group and which method of instruction has a greater impact than Speaking Skills.

Participant of the study

Participant of the study will be 60 Female students homogeneous at AlkowmAla'hmar Secondary School. They will be divided into two groups: group one experimental (30) Female students which uses Online Discussion, and group two control (30) Female students which is submitted to conventional method.

Table 1: Table of the sample of the Study

Group	Method of Teaching	Number
Experimental	Using Online discussion	30
Control	Using conventional method	30
Total		60

Instruments of the study

Three instruments will be used to carry out this study

1. A pre-test will be provided prior to the application of the treatment to determine the level of female students.
2. A post-test will be given following the treatment to see if using Online Discussion has any effect on the experimental group, and which kind of instruction has a greater impact on the subjects than the other.
3. A questionnaire will be used to find the students' attitudes toward using Online Discussion.

Validity of the instruments

The instruments will be given to a number of experts including professors and teachers to determine the instrument's accuracy, clarity, validity, and appropriateness; after that, the instrument will be modified in accordance with their recommendations, Reliability of the instrument. The researcher will utilize a test-retest procedure on a pilot study with two weeks' period to determine the instruments' reliability.

Reliability of the instrument

To determine the instrument's reliability, the investigator will utilize a test-retest on a pilot study with three weeks' period between the test and retest.

Variables of the study

The variables in the study are as follows:

- 1- The independent variables of this study will be:
 - A- Teaching Speaking Skills via Online Discussion.
 - B- Teaching Speaking traditionally
- 2- The dependent variable of this study will be:
 - A- Female Students' Speaking Skills performance.
 - 3- Female Student's Attitude Toward Using Online Discussion in Teaching Speaking Skills.

Procedures of the Study

This study will adapt the quasi-experimental methodology. Two groups of Female students of the Ninth grade will be chosen. A pre-test will be provided to the students to determine their level of speaking skills. The first group will learn Speaking Skills using Online Discussion mode (experimental group). The second group will learn Speaking Skills using regular instruction (control group). After conducting the classes and activities, a post test will be given to the Female students. Then, the post test will be scored, and the scores will be tabulated and prepared for statistical analysis.

Statistical Analysis

To achieve the study's aims, the required statistical analysis will be carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. For all study variables, including method, means, standard deviations, and ANOVA statistical analysis will be performed (using Online Discussion versus regular instruction).

And The Statistical Program (SPSS) will be used to extract the results of the questionnaire distributed to the study sample, where arithmetic averages, standard deviations and analysis of multiple and rank variance were used for each of the paragraphs of the study tool and each field of the tool, and the tool as a whole to know the trends of female students.

Discussion

Finding Related to the First Question:

Are there significant differences between mean scores of the experimental and control groups 9th Grade Female students' performance in the students' learning Speaking Skills due to the method of using (Using Online Discussion VS the conventional method)?

To answer this question, the researcher tested the first hypothesis of the study which reads. "There are statistically significant differences between the experimental group and control group students' mean scores in speaking at $\alpha \leq 0.05$ due to the to the method of using (Using Online Discussion VS the conventional method)?"

To test this hypothesis, the researcher used independent sample T-test to compare between groups (control, experimental) for pre-test + post-test, table (2) shows that.

Table (2) Result of Independent sample T Test for Pre-Test Group (Control vs Experimental)

Test	Group	N	Mean	Std. deviation	DF	T	Sig
Pre-test (speaking)	Control	16	16.45	1.62	30	1.34	0.23

	Experimental	16	17.50	1.78			
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Table (2) shows there is not statistically significant difference between control and experimental group for pre-test because the value of $T(30) = 1.02$, sig. = 0.182 for listening test and the value of $T(30) = 1.34$, sig. = 0.23 for speaking test, this evidence there is not statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the control and experimental group for pre-test. After 8 weeks, both groups sat to the same test re-named a post test a post to find out of progress of both students' speaking level and in favor of experimental group.

Table (3) Result of Independent Sample T Test for Post-test Group (Control vs Experimental)

Test	Group	N	Mean	Std. deviation	DF	T	Sig
Post-test (speaking)	Control	16	19.12	2.21	30	5.35	.000*
	Experimental	16	35.22	2.26			
Post-test (speaking)	Control	16	18.70	3.02	30	6.41	0.00*
	Experimental	16	30.34	3.12			

Table (3) shows there is a significant difference between control and experimental group for post-test because the value of $T(30) = 5.35$, sig. = 0.00 for speaking test and the value of $T(30) = 6.41$, sig. = 0.00 between the speaking test, this is an evidence that there is a statistically significant difference between the mean control and experimental group for post-test. The difference is in favor for the experimental group.

Finding Related to the Second Question

Are there any significant differences between the experimental group and control group 9th Grade Female students' mastery of Speaking Skills learning due to using Online Discussion to explained speaking Skills?

To answer this question, the researcher tested the second hypothesis of the study which reads "There are statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the experimental group students' (speaking skills) skills at $\alpha \leq 0.05$ due to using Online Discussion to explained speaking Skills?"

To test this hypothesis, the researcher used independent sample T-test to compare between tests (for post-test, table (4) shows that.

Table (4) Result of Independent Sample T Test for Post-Test Group (Listening Vs Speaking)

Tests	N	Mean	Std. deviation	DF	T	Sig
Speaking	16	30.34	3.964	30	-4.35	.000

Table (4) shows that there is a statistically significant difference between the experimental group students mastery of the speaking skills (Speaking) for post-test because the value of $T(30) = -4.35$, sig. = 0.00.

Finding Related to the Third Question

What are the experimental group Female students' attitudes toward using Online Discussion and its effect on their Attitude Toward it?

To answer this question, the researcher tested the third hypothesis of the study which reads "The experimental group students have positive attitude towards using Online Discussion and its effects on their Attitude Toward it

Mean and standard deviation for questionnaire

Table (5) Means and Standard Deviations for Each Item

No.	Statement	Mean	SD
1	Using online discussion achieved my academic goals.	3.7576	.70844
2	I enjoyed the challenge of learning new material in my courses via using online discussion .	3.1212	1.24392
3	I enjoyed learning with using online discussion into a small English community	3.5152	1.06423
4	I liked working in groups with using online discussion into a small English community	3.6667	1.05079
5	I enjoyed studying authentic aspect in the classroom.	3.3939	1.08799
6	I liked spending a lot of time by using online discussion.	3.4545	1.06334
7	Using online discussion helps me doing my homework	3.4848	.65665
8	I liked reading materials by using online discussion	2.6364	1.24545
9	Using online discussion helps me to save learning time.	3.2424	1.00095
10	Using online discussion helped me in using aesthetic aspects of language (figure of speech, idiomatic	3.3939	.86384

	expression, saying, proverbs, puzzles and jokes)		
11	I liked listening stories within using online discussion	3.4242	1.03169
12	I liked reading and sharing authentic material with other students with using online discussion .	3.3636	1.16775
13	using online discussion	3.6364	.92932
14	Using online discussion very effective for me	3.9091	.80482
15	I felt happy in this new experience of using online discussion.	3.3723	.47507
16	Using online discussion helps me to prepare for the examination	3.5455	.97118
17	Using online discussion into a small English community was a fantastic experience	3.5152	1.06423
18	I improved my vocabulary by using online discussion.	3.5455	.86930
19	Using online discussion improved my social relations and self confidence	3.5455	.86930
20	Using online discussion made me ready for help and group work.	3.1818	1.01411
21	Using online discussion helped me learn new lexicons.	3.3939	.96629
22	Using online discussion pronouncing words accurately with appropriate mechanics of speaking	3.3636	1.16775
23	Using online discussion helped me in using authentic English naturally with very few communication breakdown: e.g. hesitation and fillers, etc	3.6364	.92932
24	Using online discussion helped me in using body language and facial expressions effectively to aid meaning	3.9091	.80482
25	Using online discussion helped me in using grammatical structure and difficult lexicons	3.3723	.47507
	Total	3.51	.321

Table (5) shows the mean and standard deviation for each item: The range means for items of this domain is between (2.64 – 3.90), the higher means for item (Using online discussion helped me in using body language and facial expressions effectively to aid meaning.), but the lower means for item (I liked reading materials by using online discussion) Total means was (3.51) by moderate agreement.

Discussions of the Results of the First Question

The first question of the study investigated if there were any statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the experimental and control groups in language speaking due to the method of using (Using Online Discussion VS the conventional method The findings of the study have revealed that using online discussion VS the conventional method was a very effective method to develop language speaking.

Discussion of the Results of the second Question

The second question of the study tried to investigate the students' mastery of Speaking Skills. Did the experimental group develop more as a result of using Online Discussion to explained speaking Skills?

The result of the study revealed that the experimental group students developed their both skills (speaking). This might be due to the fact that speaking fluency is a productive skill that needs more efforts to be developed.

Discussion of the Results of the Third Question

The third question investigated the experimental Group students' attitudes toward using Online Discussion and its effect on their Attitude Toward it

By having deep interpretation and analysis of the results of the questionnaire, the researcher found out that using Online Discussion and its effect on their Attitude Toward it had a positive effect on the experimental group students' attitudes. Accordingly, the hypothesis of the study which reads "The experimental group students have positive attitudes toward using Online Discussion and its effect on their fluency and motivation" is accepted.

Recommendations

The researcher presents the following four sub-sections: recommendations directed to ministries of education, recommendations for curricula designer, recommendations for EFL researchers, recommendation for EFL teachers. According to the finding of this study, textbook writers, researchers, teachers, and students are highly recommended to take the following of recommendations into consideration to their job successfully.

A. Recommendations Directed to Ministry of Education.

Ministry of education should equip schools and universities with laboratories provided with contemporary authentic all aspect of English community so that students have a chance to practice language as if they live in the English community. Moreover, teachers and students will be able to watch and listen to real-life situations and authentic English.

B. Recommendations Directed to Curricula Designers

Curricula designers should take into account the importance of Using Online Discussion. EFL curricula designers are recommending to use new syllabi depended on many aspects that help to change the EFL classes into a Using Online Discussion by using authentic pictures, authentic videos, authentic reading text and native speaker that develop the EFL student's fluency and motivation.

Conclusion

The following conclusion should be derived from this study

- Using online discussion should be used in teaching speaking.
- Using online discussion has more effect on the productive skill of speaking performance.
- Using online discussion is a motivating environment for language learning

References

- AlJeraisy, M. & Mohammad, H., & Fayyoumi, A., & Alrashideh, W. (2015). Web 2.0 in education: The impact of discussion board on student performance and satisfaction. **The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology**, 14(2), 247-259.
- Alzaharani, M.(2017). The Effect of Using Online Discussion Forums on Students' Learning, **The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology**, 1(16), 164- 176.
- An, H., Shin, S., & Lim, K. (2009). The effects of different instructor facilitation approaches on students' interactions during asynchronous online discussions. **Computers & Education**, 53(3), 749-760.
- Bashir, M, & Azeem, M, & Dogar, A,.(2011).Factor Effecting Students' English Speaking Skills, **British Journal of Arts and Social Sciences**, 1(2), 34-50.
- Elkhafaifi, H. (2005). Listening comprehension and anxiety in the Arabic language classroom. **The Modern Language Journal**, 88, (2), 45-69.
- Jacob, S (2012). Mathematical achievement and critical thinking skills in asynchronous discussion forums. **Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences**, 31, 800-804.
- John, L. (2002). **Language and Linguistics: An Introduction**, (15th ed.), Cambridge University Press, UK.
- Kyungbin, K& Su, J &Suhkyung, S & Chae, Y,.(2019). Effects of different types of instructor comments in online discussions. **Journal Distance Education**, 2(40),226-242.
- [Lynn, B,&Shelley S](#), & Helen M,.(2019). Reflection Using an Online Discussion Forum: Impact on Student Learning and Satisfaction, **JournalSocial Work Education**, 8(28), 841-855.
- Ravi, S,.(2014). Effectiveness of Using Online Discussion Forum for Case Study Analysis, **Education Research International**, ID 589860, 1-10.
- Zhong, S, & Chin, H, & Jiaxin Y, & Hai, j, & Song, Q & Liming, L,.(2017). Improving the English-speaking skills of young learners through mobile social networking, **Computer Assisted Language Learning**, 3(4), 304-324.

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